

Quantum Estimation Theory for Neutrino Physics

NuPhys 2026: Prospects in Neutrino Physics

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<https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.20148>

Motivation

δ_{CP} experimentally known with a big uncertainty

Does nature contain insufficient information, or are we simply unable to extract it?

Quantum Estimation Theory

Sensing in the quantum world

Quantum Metrology

The use of quantum mechanics to achieve measurement precision beyond classical limits, often by exploiting entanglement or squeezed states

Quantum Sensing

The use of quantum systems, properties, or phenomena to perform precise measurements of physical quantities

Quantum Estimation

The mathematical theory that sets the fundamental limits on how accurately a physical parameter can be estimated from measurements

Applications

- Axion dark matter: *K. M. Backes et al., Nature 590, 238 (2021), doi:10.1038/s41586-021-03226-7*
- QED scattering experiments: *Asenov, Zhang & Serafini, arXiv:2506.23197, (2025)*
- Collider phenomenology: *T. Ai et al., Phys. Rev. Lett. 135, 241804 (2025)*
- Cosmological parameters: *Piotrak et al., arXiv:2507.12228 (2025)*

Quantum Estimation Theory

Fundamental bounds
on estimators

Quantifies the
amount of
information in the
quantum state and
in the observable

Tells us if a
measurement
strategy is optimal

Metrology Protocol

λ \rightarrow set of parameters that we want to estimate

not observables!

Cramér-Rao Bound

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\lambda}) \underset{\substack{\text{Classical} \\ \downarrow}}{\geq} \frac{1}{NF(\lambda)} \underset{\substack{\text{Quantum} \\ \downarrow}}{\geq} \frac{1}{NH(\lambda)}$$

Fisher Information (FI)

- Function of $p(x|\lambda)$
- Measurement **dependent**
- Information in the **quantum state** and in the **observable**

Quantum Fisher Information (QFI)

- Function of $|\psi_\lambda\rangle$
- Measurement **independent**
- Information in the **quantum state** only

Some formulas

- The FI is given by:

$$F(\lambda) = \sum_x \frac{1}{p(x|\lambda)} \left(\frac{\partial p(x|\lambda)}{\partial \lambda} \right)^2$$

according to the Born rule $p(x|\lambda) = |\langle x|\psi_\lambda\rangle|^2$

- The QFI for pure states

$$H(\lambda) = 4\langle \partial_\lambda \psi_\lambda | \partial_\lambda \psi_\lambda \rangle - 4|\langle \partial_\lambda \psi_\lambda | \psi_\lambda \rangle|^2$$

A new tool

- Allows us to define fundamental bounds on estimators → **Cramér-Rao**
- Quantifies the amount of information in the quantum state and in the observable measured → **QFI and FI**
- Tells us if a measurement strategy is optimal → **FI vs QFI**
- Simple and straightforward application

Motivation

- We started from the big uncertainty on δ_{CP} : we wanted to study if the large uncertainty on it was due to a lack of information in the quantum state of the neutrino or in the measurement strategy

Quantum Estimation Theory

Metrology Protocol for Neutrinos

$\lambda =$ PMNS matrix parameters

QFI

- Neutrinos propagating as **plane waves** in **vacuum**
- ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ beams \longrightarrow **independent** experiments

Quantum Fisher Information

- QFI maxima close to probability oscillation maxima
- No dependence on the value of δ_{CP}
- Consistent sensitivity across oscillation maxima
- $N = O(10^3) \Rightarrow \sigma \approx 3^\circ$

Flavour Measurement

The only available

Flavour measurement:

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi_e &= |\nu_e\rangle\langle\nu_e| & \Pi_\mu &= |\nu_\mu\rangle\langle\nu_\mu| \\ \Pi_{off} &= \mathbb{I} - \Pi_e - \Pi_\mu & &= |\nu_\tau\rangle\langle\nu_\tau|\end{aligned}$$

$$p(\beta|\lambda) = |\langle\nu_\beta|\nu_{\alpha\lambda}(t)\rangle|^2 \longrightarrow \text{FI}$$

Fisher Information for a Flavor Measurement

- QFI
- $\delta_{CP} = \delta_{NO}$
- · - $\delta_{CP} = 0$
- - $\delta_{CP} = \pi/2$

- Flavour measurement is **not optimal**
- Depends on δ_{CP} and increase with oscillations
- **More information** at the **second peak** than the first
- Experiments at the peak are not optimal for $\delta_{CP} = \pi/2$

See also *P. Coloma and E. Fernandez-Martinez, JHEP 2012:89 (2012)*

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What about the other parameters?

— FI
- - - QFI

— FI
- - - QFI

Conclusions

- We identify the underlying **information-theoretic constraints** responsible for the large uncertainty on δ_{CP} : **flavour measurement is not optimal** for the estimation of the CP violating phase while it is for the mixing angles
- Our results were obtained with a **general and simple framework**:

Very few ingredients \rightarrow

- ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ quantum state
- Formalization of the flavour measurements
- QFI and FI formulas

- Diagnostic power of the application of QET to Neutrino Physics and High Energy Physics

Outlooks: A Diagnostic Tool

- Matter effects
- Detection efficiencies
- Full energy spectrum
- Wave packets description and decoherence
- Multiparameter
- Test BSM scenario for neutrinos

How these specific factors degrade the Fisher Information relative to the ultimate quantum bound?

Thank you!

Check it out!

M. Ignati, C. Frugiuele, M. G. A. Paris, M. G. Genoni, “Is the large uncertainty of δ_{CP} fundamentally encoded in the neutrino quantum state?”, arXiv:2511.20148 (2025)

Backup

Appearance vs Disappearance vs Idealized

Comparison

QFI comparison

Electronic Quantum State

Optimal measurement

Optimal measurement: projection over the eigenstates of the Symmetric Logarithmic Derivative (SLD)

$$\partial_\lambda \rho_\lambda = \frac{L_\lambda \rho_\lambda + \rho_\lambda L_\lambda}{2}$$

$$H(\lambda) \equiv \text{Tr}[\rho_\lambda L_\lambda^2] = \text{Tr}[\partial_\lambda \rho_\lambda L_\lambda]$$

Optimal quantum estimator:

$$O_\lambda = \mathbb{I}\lambda + \frac{L_\lambda}{H(\lambda)}$$

What did we consider?

- Neutrinos propagating in vacuum \rightarrow T2K/T2HK and ESS ν SB
- Ideal flavour measurements \rightarrow Ultimate bounds
 - Information from all oscillation channels
 - Efficiencies equal to one
- Neutrino and antineutrino mode \rightarrow Independent experiments
- Figure of merits: $\frac{H_{\bar{\nu}} + H_{\nu}}{2}$ and $\frac{F_{\bar{\nu}} + F_{\nu}}{2}$

Dependence on δ_{CP}

QFI Derivation

$$\begin{aligned} F(\lambda) &\leq \int dx \left| \frac{\text{Tr} [\rho_\lambda \Pi_x L_\lambda]}{\sqrt{\text{Tr} [\rho_\lambda \Pi_x]}} \right|^2 \\ &= \int dx \left| \text{Tr} \left[\frac{\sqrt{\rho_\lambda} \sqrt{\Pi_x}}{\sqrt{\text{Tr} [\rho_\lambda \Pi_x]}} \sqrt{\Pi_x} L_\lambda \sqrt{\rho_\lambda} \right] \right|^2 \\ &\leq \int dx \text{Tr} [\Pi_x L_\lambda \rho_\lambda L_\lambda] \\ &= \text{Tr} [L_\lambda \rho_\lambda L_\lambda] \\ &= \text{Tr} [\rho_\lambda L_\lambda^2] \end{aligned}$$

Biased Estimator

Cramér-Rao: $\text{Var}(\hat{\lambda}) \geq \frac{[1 + b'(\lambda)]^2}{F(\lambda)} \geq \frac{[1 + b'(\lambda)]^2}{H(\lambda)}$ where $E\{\hat{\lambda}\} = b(\lambda) + \lambda$

if $b'(\lambda) < 0$ the lower bound is smaller than for an unbiased estimator

Quantify the bias from experimental results

Take advantage of a negative bias

Future work may include a study of the bias